

**A HYBRIDIZED APPROACH FOR RISK DETECTION USING GENETIC AND
DECISION TREE ALGORITHMS GA-DTA****Umejuru Daniel***

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chigoziri.marcus@uniport.edu.ng***Corresponding Author: Umejuru Daniel****ABSTRACT**

Risk detection has been challenging in the networking domain and requires stringent security addressing. The trend in recent times for users to progressively adopt evolving information technologies has become a key measure in combating challenging risk in the network space. In this research, a hybridized framework combining Decision Tree and Genetic Algorithms known as the GA-DTA was developed to detect risk in network traffic environment. A genetic algorithm fitness function was used and fitness values computed too based on accuracy, simplicity, support and attribute gain ratio to generate optimal features for the decision tree optimization. A classifier, C4.5 algorithm is used to train KDD Cup 99 dataset and generate a streamlined decision trees shown as ordered lists of rule based policy on network. Object- oriented analysis and design methodology (OOADM) was used as methodology while implementation was done with Java programming language. Experimental phases were tested using WEKA open-source tool to compare the proposed hybrid approach with other techniques. The obtained results showed that compared to C4.5, Random Forest, and GA that the GA-DTA hybrid algorithm performed better with improved detection accuracy of 99.59%, and reduced false value rate of 6.45% as lowest. The hybridized model has proven that risk detection using the combined algorithms fared better than other existing models.

Keywords:

Data, Security, Risk, Integrity, Detection, Network

1. INTRODUCTION

Data is the primary source of strength or weakness of an organization. It is capable of sustaining an organization when handled with care, and has the ability to destroy an organization when handled with carelessness. The existence of any organization or corporation is directly proportional to the existence of such organization's uncompromised sensitive data. Nevertheless, the fastest and easiest way a company's image and lifespan can be ruined or cut short is through data leakage. Therefore, data, as one of the organization's most valuable assets must be well managed, maximally protected, and jealously guided to maintain its integrity (Jang- Jaccard and Nepal, 2024). Integrity has always been what great organization's protect throughout their existence. It is almost impossible for such organizations that have high esteem for their brand to compromise it. They do this by securing their sensitive data with all amount of seriousness, carrying out checks and balances in every activity carried out on accurately timed manner. Maintaining data integrity is a serious task in every sphere of life. This is because we are faced with dynamic ways in which it can be negotiated especially in a corporate networked environment, as we are in a global village. Therefore, we must device means to prevent and block whatever loopholes, actions and calculated attempts that can be used to break it. This is where security comes into play (Shouhuai, 2024).

2. THEORITICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Genetic Algorithm

Genetic algorithm (GA) is a search method based on the mechanics of natural selection and neutral genetics, used for finding the optimal or near optimal solutions in a reasonable amount of time. Note that the solution returned by a genetic algorithm is almost never optimal; it is close to optimality (Chahar et al., 2021). However, searching through all possible solutions for the optimal one would take an unacceptable amount of time as opposed to a genetic algorithm. Genetic Algorithm combines survival of fittest among string structures with a structure yet randomized information exchange to form a search algorithm with some of the innovative flair of human search. In every generation, a new set of artificial creatures (string) is created using bits and pieces of the fittest of the old. An occasional new part is then tried for good measure (Federico et al., 2023). They efficiently exploit historical information to speculate on a new search points with expected improved performance. GA's begin with a set of k randomly generated states, called population. Each state, or individual, is represented as a string over a finite alphabet, more commonly, a string of 0's and 1's. This representation of an individual is called a chromosome. For the production of next generation of states, each state is rated by the fitness function. A fitness function should return higher values for better states.

The GA has many differences from more normal optimization and search procedures in:

- i. GAs work with a coding of the parameter set, not parameter themselves. The GAs require the natural parameter set of the optimization problem to be coded as a finite-length string over some finite alphabet (Al- Ghazal et al., 2023).
- ii. GAs search from a population of points not a single point.
- iii. GAs use payoff (objective function) information, not derivatives or other auxiliary knowledge.
- iv. GAs use probabilistic transition rules not deterministic rules .A canonical genetic algorithm is composed of three operators: Reproduction, Crossover, and Mutation.

2.2 Genetic Algorithm Representation

The GA contains only one main data structure: *population* of individuals. Each individual affectionately known as a critter represents an element with the domain of the solution space of the optimization problem. The individuals in GA are simply finite length strings of bits. Each string of 1s' and 0s' is called *chromosomes* for fixed length n . The chromosome of a given critter is the only source for all the information about the corresponding solution. Since the variable values are represented as binary, there must be a way of converting continuous values into binary values and vice versa (Suhas 2021). The difference between the actual function value and the quantization measure is known as the quantization error. The mathematical formulae for the binary encoding and decoding of the *n*th variable P_n are given as follows:

For encoding:

$$P_{norm} = \frac{P_n - P_{min}}{P_{max} - P_{min}} \quad (1)$$

For decoding:

$Chromosome[m]$	$round \left\{ \frac{P_{norm} - 2^{-m}}{2^{-m}} \sum_{p=1}^{m-1} Chromosome [p] \times 2^{-p} \right\}$	
	$Chromosome[m] \times \frac{P_{max} - P_{min}}{2^{m+1}} = \sum_{m=1}^n 2^{-m} + 2^{-m}$	
	$Q_n = P_{quant} (P_{max} - P_{min})$	(2)

In each case, P_{norm} is a normalized variable within the range $0 \leq P_{norm} \leq 1$. P_{min} is the minimum variable's value. P_{max} is the maximum variable's value. $Chromosome[m]$ is the binary version of P_n . $round\{\}$ is rounding the variable's value to the nearest integer value. P_{quant} is the quantized version of P_{norm} . Q_n is the quantized version of P_n . Typically, this means that a string of **1s** and **0s** are used to present the decision variables, the collection of which represents a potential solution to the problem.

Parents	Children
000 000	000 111
111 111	111 000

(Table 1. Single Crossover Reproduction)

Parents	Children
000 000 00	000 111 00
111 111 11	111 000 11

(Table 2. Multiple Crossover Reproduction)

Initially a population of individuals, P is created. Although different approaches can be used to perform this step, they typically are generated randomly. From this population, a new population, P' , of the same size is created. The algorithm repeatedly selects individuals from whom create new ones. These parents i_1, i_2 are then used to produce two offspring, o_1, o_2 using crossover process. Then mutants may be generated.

The process continues until the new population satisfies the termination condition. In genetic algorithms, reproduction is defined by precise algorithms that indicate how to combine the given set of individuals to produce new ones. These are called crossover algorithm. Given two individual parents from the population, the crossover technique generates new individuals (offspring or children) by switching subsequences of the strings (Pironti 2024). Table 2.2 and 2.3 illustrates the process of crossover.

A genetic algorithm pseudocode is presented in Algorithm 1

Algorithm 1: Genetic Algorithm	
	Require: population, a set of individuals FITNESS, a function that measures fitness of an individual
Step 1:	Begin: newpopulation ← emptyset
Step 2:	for $i \leftarrow 1$ to $SIZE(population)$ do $x \leftarrow SELECT(population, FITNESS)$ $y \leftarrow$ $SELECT(population, FITNESS)$ $child \leftarrow$ $REPRODUCE(x, y)$
Step 3:	if small random probability then $child$ $\leftarrow MUTATE(child)$ end if
Step 4:	add $child$ to newpopulation end for
Step 5:	$population \leftarrow$ newpopulation end while
Step 6:	Output: return the best individual in the population, according to FITNESS

2.3 Decision Tree

A decision tree is a flow-chart-like tree structure, where each internal node (non-leaf node) denotes a test on attribute, each branch represents an outcome of the test, and each leaf node (or terminal node) holds a class label.

Assuming that S is the set of data samples, the attributes of class label have m different values, and the number of different classes $C_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, m)$ to be m . Set S_i is the number of samples in class C_i . For a given sample, the expected information needed for classification is given by the following equation:

$$I(S_1, S_2, \dots, S_m) = - \sum_{i=1}^m p_i \log_2(p_i), \tag{1}$$

where $p_i = S_i/S$ is the probability of any sample belonging to C_i .

Set attribute A with v different values $\{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_v\}$. Then S could be divided into v subsets $\{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_v\}$ by attribute A . Where the sample of S_j has the same value $a_j(1, 2, \dots, v)$ in the attribute A . Set S_{ij} to be the number of the sample of class C_i in a subset S_j . The entropy and information expectations of the subsets divided by A are given by the following expression:

When the entropy value is smaller, the purity of subset partition will be higher. For a given subset S_j , the expected information is:

$$I(S_{1j}, S_{2j}, \dots, S_{mj}) = - \sum_{i=1}^m p_{ij} \log_2(p_{ij}) \tag{2}$$

where $p_{ij} = S_{ij} / S_j$ is the probability of the sample of S_j belonging to C_i . If we conduct the branch operation in the attribute A , the information gain received is

$$\text{Gain}(A) = (S_{I_j}, S_{I_j}, \dots, S_{m_j}) - E(A) \quad (3) \quad 2.4$$

Decision Tree Algorithms

The classical decision tree algorithm includes ID3 algorithm, C4.5 algorithm based on ID3 algorithm, CHAID algorithm (CHI-squared Automatic Interaction Detector), and CART algorithm (Classification and Regression Tree) (Song and Lu, 2025).

C4.5 algorithm is a modified algorithm based on ID3. Compared to ID3 algorithm, C4.5 algorithm can describe the continual attribute situation, but ID3 algorithm cannot. And C4.5 algorithm has a faster speed in realizing the process than ID3 algorithm. Moreover the decision tree structure of C4.5 is also more reasonable than ID3 algorithm and also finds the good rules information. Compared to CART decision tree algorithm, C4.5 can construct multitree and CART algorithm only construct binary tree.

As we all know C4.5 is a modified algorithm to generate decision tree based on ID3 algorithm. C5.0/See 5.0 is commercialized versions of C4.5; the core of C5.0/See 5.0 is the same with C4.5, but C5.0/See 5.0 has been modified in execution efficiency and memory.

Algorithm 2: Rule Expression for Decision Tree

IF (age = youth) and (student = no) then Class = B
IF (age = youth) and (student = yes) then Class = A
IF (age = middle-age) then Class =
IF (age = senior) and (credit-rating = excellent) then Class = B

Based on C4.5, C5.0 algorithm not only includes all functions of C4.5, but also introduces many new technologies. Particularly, one of the most important technologies is boosting technique which further improves the recognition rate of the sample (Chiang, 2022). Compared with C4.5, C5.0 with higher accuracy, faster running speed, and smaller decision tree model takes up less computer memory

3. METHODOLOGY

To achieve the objectives of this work, we adopt a hybrid approach combining Genetic Algorithm (GA) and a Decision Tree Algorithm (DTA). Hence, the proposed GA-DTA model. Genetic Algorithm is a search technique that is used to find an appropriate solution to search problems. It mimics natural selection and neutral genetics, used for finding the optimal or near-optimal solutions in a reasonable amount of time. However, it is important to note that the solution returned by a genetic algorithm is almost never optimal; it is close to optimality hence the needs for this hybrid approach. Genetic algorithms have been applied in anomaly detection in many ways, as they are flexible and a powerful search method. A decision tree on the other hand, is a flow-chart-like tree structure, where each internal node (non-leaf node) denotes a test on attribute, each branch represents an outcome of the test, and each leaf node (or terminal node) holds a class label. The topmost node in a tree is the root node. The decision tree algorithm usually has three popular attribute selection measures, namely, information gain, gain ratio, and gini index. Searching through all possible solutions for the optimal one would take an unacceptable amount of time as opposed to a genetic algorithm.

The GA-DTA model presents a framework to optimize and simplify the search rules of more complex combinations of the C4.5 algorithm using GA optimization. This also enhances the efficiency in space of search rules C4.5 decision tree algorithm has.

3.1 Algorithm of Proposed Model

Algorithm 3: GA-DTA *Input:* Dataset R , Parameters for Genetic algorithm

- Step 1:** Initialize population; Scan R , select records where class attribute value= C_i
- Begin:**
 $I=0$;
 Initialize $P(I)$;
- Step 2:** Perform preprocessing operation (clean data, discretize continuous attributes, calculate each feature attribute information gain rate, code recorded data Preprocessing R ;
- Step 3:** Select preprocessed data R as an input to C4.5 for generating initial population of pruned decision trees
- Step 4:** Create a given root node for the given tree
- Step 5:** If all dataset are positive return the single-node tree root, with label = +
- Step 6:** If all dataset are negative return the single-node tree root, with label = -
- Step 7:** If attribute is empty, return the single-node tree Root, with label = most common value of Target attribute in dataset
- Step 8:** Select the classifiers
- Step 9:** A the attribute from Attributes that best classifies the dataset
- Step 10:** The decision attributes for Root A
- Step 11:** Calculate entropy, information gain, gain ratio of attributes.
- Step 12:** For each given value v_i , Insert a new branch of the tree below the Root that corresponds to the test $A = v_i$
- Step 13:** Let dataset v_i be subset of dataset that have value v_i for A
- Step 14:** If dataset v_i is empty, then below the new branch, add a leaf node with label = most common value of Target_attribute in Dataset
- Step 15:** Else, below this new branch add the subtree
Goto Step 4
-
- Step 14:** Tree generator generates the pruned decision tree
- Step 15:** Compute the fitness value of each tree (each individual in the population) and find the average fitness.
 $Fitness P(I)$;
 $Avg(Fitness P(I))$;
- Step 16:** Select individuals based on fitness and apply crossover and mutation to selected individuals, creating new trees. Compute the fitness value of each new tree and update the current population (new individuals replace previous individuals).
 While ($I \leq Max_generation$ or $Avg_i - Avg_{i-1} > \epsilon$)
 {
 $I++$;

*GA-Operation P(I);**Fitness P(I);*

}

Or delete the individual which fitness less than the threshold value;

Step 17: Get the optimal classification rules and calculate the average the *Fitness(I)***Output:**Optimal Population *P(I)*;**Step 18:** END

The process starts with initializing the population by randomly selecting a sample R from the training set, whose class attribute value is C_i . Then the evolution algebra variable number I , and the population initial average fitness variable Avg are both assigned zero. Then preprocessing operations are conducted on the sample R , including data cleaning, continuous attribute discretization, calculating the information gain ratios of each feature attribute, and encoding the record data. C4.5 algorithm shown in Algorithm 4 is then used to generate the decision tree encoded as the initial population $P(r)$.

C4.5 contains a mechanism to re-express decision trees as ordered lists of IF- THEN rules and each of the path gives the condition that must be satisfied if a case is to be classified by that leaf. C4.5 generalizes this prototype rule by dropping any conditions that are irrelevant to the class, guided again by the heuristic for estimating true error rates. The set of rules is reduced further based on the Minimum Description Length (MDL) principle for pruning decision trees described above. Next, we check if the value of I is less than the maximum evolution population. If this is true, the following computation is performed:

- i. The average fitness of this generation is calculated and selection, crossover, and mutation operations are performed on this population to generate the offspring population.
- ii. The individuals that have high fitness in the offspring population replaces the ones with low fitness in the parent; therefore, new generation is formed.
- iii. The fitness of each individual in the new generation is computed as well as the average fitness.
- iv. These steps are repeated until the value of I is less than the maximum evolution population or $Avg_i - Avg_{i-1} > \epsilon$. Otherwise, those individuals whose fitness value is less than the lowest fitness threshold are taken out. The result is the optimized population, which is the optimal set of rules. The Work flow diagram illustrating the GA-DTA model as described here is shown in figure 3.1

Figure 3.1: Workflow of proposed GA-DTA system

- i. *Password problems* - Many individuals do not get along easily with passwords as most people still use 123456 or 0000 as their password, In addition to not creating strong, unique passwords, untrained users commit many other password mistakes including writing down passwords on post-it notes on their monitors or sharing them with colleagues.
- ii. *Patching* – Cyber-criminals are constantly looking for new exploits in software. When exploits are discovered, the software developers race to fix the vulnerability and send out the patch to all users before cyber-criminals can compromise more users. This is why it is essential that users install security updates on their computers as soon as they are available.
- iii. *Physical security errors* - While data breaches are most often attributed to cyber attacks, organizations are also liable to physical threats. Confidential information and credentials can be stolen or viewed by unauthorized persons if they gain access to secure premises. Physical security errors come in many different forms, but one of the most common is leaving sensitive documents unattended on desks, meeting rooms or even printer output trays.

4. RESULTS

Figure 4.1: Main interface with warning when there is no internet connectivity

Figure 4.2: Dashboard showing human error related threats

Figure 4.3: Dashboard showing no threat

Figure 4.4: Result showing comparison based on accuracy rate

Figure 4.5: Result showing comparison based on false value rate

Detection Accuracy of different models with corresponding human factor partitions as shown in Table 4.1. We can see that the accuracy of GA-DTA algorithm in the training data is 99.39%, 99.48, 99.52% and 99.59% for patching errors, physical security errors, password problems and misdelivery respectively. Although accuracy is varying from one partition to another partition, the highest accuracy of 99.59% was achieved in case of GA-DTA for the training set. The result also indicates that misdelivery is the most common kind of human error with high vulnerability in the selected training set data.

Models Compared	Patching Errors %	Physical Security Errors %	Password Problems %	Misdelivery %
GA-DTA	99.39	99.48	99.52	99.59
C4.5	99.29	99.33	99.43	99.05
Random Forest	98.55	98.86	98.38	99.12
GA	97.75	97.92	97.45	97.86

(Table 4.1 Result showing accuracy rate for various algorithms)

DISCUSSION

Fig 4.1 shows the main interface with the warning that there is no internet connectivity in the GA-DTA simulation application. Fig 4.2 shows the no human error related threats. Fig 4.3 shows the no threat at all interface. Fig 4.4 shows the accuracy rate graph of all techniques with the proposed hybridized GA-DTA performing best at 99.59%. Finally 4.5 shows false value rate graph with the proposed hybridized GA-DTA having the lowest false value rate of 6.45%.

5. CONCLUSION

The results obtained from our experiment revealed that our system has in this work proffered a hybridized approach as an improvement to other existing models. The system takes advantage of Genetic algorithm optimization ability to optimize the results generated by a decision tree classifier and the classifier used is C4.5 Algorithm. We constructed the process of this algorithm firstly, and then we did an experiment with the algorithm. KDD cup 99 dataset was used to test the algorithms using four categories of attribute features such as misdelivery, physical errors, password problems and patching. The experiment was performed using WEKA 3.9 tool and performance advantages over existing systems as follows: GA-DTA hybrid algorithm showed improved detection accuracy of 99.59% compared to 99.05% for C4.5, 99.12% for Random forest, and 97.86 for Genetic algorithm. GA-DTA has the lowest false value rate of 6.45% as lowest, indicating a significant reduction as compared to C4.5 with 7.54%, Random Forest with 7.89%, and the highest false value rate of 9.46% for Genetic algorithm. With the results shown, we conclude that the hybridized model has proven that risk detection using the combined algorithm fared better than other existing models.

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